

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART VI. STRUCTURE OF THE
CADINENIC SESQUITERPENE PRESENT IN THE OIL FROM
THE OLEO-RESIN OF *HARDWICKIA PINNATA*

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A *dextro*-rotatory cadinenic sesquiterpene has been isolated from the essential oil of *Hardwickia pinnata*. Its structure has been established and has been shown to be a structural isomer, rather than a stereoisomer, of *l-α*-cadinene.

In Part V of this series of papers (Sukh Dev and Guha, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 495) it has been shown that the essential oil from the oleo-resin of *Hardwickia pinnata* contains about 2% of a *dextro*-rotatory sesquiterpene, which yields *l*-cadinene dihydrochloride. It has been remarked there that the hydrocarbon may be a structural isomer of *l-α*-cadinene capable of giving the same dihydrochloride. This has been found to be the actual case.

In the literature a large number of cadinenic sesquiterpenes with varying optical rotations has been described [(a) "Handbuch der Pflanzen-analyse", dritter band/erste halfte, spezielle analyse II, p. 602, 1932 Ed. (b) Egloff, "Physical Constants of Hydrocarbons", Vol. II, p. 486, 1940 Ed.]. Out of these the *dextro*-rotatory hydrocarbons have been supposed to represent *d*-cadinene. It is quite likely that some of these may represent the stereoisomer of *l-α*-cadinene, but others may be the structural isomers (with *dextro* rotation) of this hydrocarbon, which can give rise to *l*-cadinene dihydrochloride. Deussen has described a "*d*-cadinene", isolated from West Indian Sandalwood oil (Deussen, *Annalen*, 1912, 388; 145; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1929, ii, 120, 121; Simonsen, "The Terpenes", Vol. II, p. 506, 1932 Ed.), which gives *l*-cadinene derivatives. He has suggested that probably during the treatment with hydrogen halides, an inversion takes place. Ordinarily, optical inversions of the Walden type are restricted to substitution reactions involving an asymmetric carbon atom (Gilman, "Organic Chemistry, an Advanced Treatise", Vol. I, p. 265, 1945 Ed.). It is more likely that Deussen's "*d*-cadinene" represents a structural isomer of *l-α*-cadinene, which can yield the *l*-cadinene derivatives. This appears to be supported by the fact that Grimal (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, 135, 1057) has isolated a *dextro*-rotatory sesquiterpene from Atlas Cedarwood oil* which gives derivatives of cadinene having *dextro* rotations. He has further regenerated the hydrocarbon from the *dextro*-rotatory dihydrochloride, and has obtained a *d*-hydrocarbon. Probably Grimal's *d*-hydrocarbon represents the true *d*-cadinene. The properties of these hydrocarbons have been compared in Table I. Since the *dextro*-rotatory cadinenic hydrocarbon from the *Hardwickia pinnata* oil gives derivatives of *l*-cadinene, it was thought of interest to investigate it fully.

* Recently, Ruzicka, Schinz and Muller (*Helv Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 195) have isolated from Atlas Cedar-leaf oil a *d*-hydrocarbon, which gives a dihydrochloride, m p. 117-18°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, -7.9 The sesquiterpene isolated from the pure dihydrochloride has $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +67.2. This hydrocarbon has been shown by these investigators as not belonging to the cadalene group.

TABLE I

Hydrocarbon.	B.p.	[α] _D .	Dihydrochloride.		Dihydrobromide.	
			M.p.	[α] _D .	M.p.	[α] _D .
1. <i>l</i> -Cadinene.*	134-36°/11 mm.	-125.2	117-18°	-36.24	124-25°†	-36.13
2. <i>d</i> -Cadinene.** (Deusse.).	138-40°/13 mm	+38.72	117-18°	-36.24	124-25°	-36.13
3. <i>d</i> -Cadinene.*** (Grimal).	273°-275°	+48.7	117-18°	+8°54' (chloroform) +25°40' (ethyl acetate),	124-25°	+rotatory.
4. <i>d</i> -Cadinene†† (Grimal, re- generated from the <i>d</i> -cadinene dihydrochloride).	274°-275°	+47.55	—	—	—	—
5. <i>d</i> -Cadinene.† (Thurber and Roll, regenera- ted from the di- hydrochloride, m.p. 118°).	272°-274°	+103.7	—	—	—	—

* Henderson and Robertson, *J Chem.Soc.*, 1924, 1992.

** Deussen, *loc. cit.*

*** Grimal, *Compt. rend.*, 1902, 188, 1057.

†† Grimal *loc. cit.*

† Thurber and Roll, *Ind. Eng.Chem.*, 1927, 19, 739

‡ Wallach, *Annalen*, 1887, 288, 86.

The cadinenic fraction of the oil from the oleo-resin of *Hardwickia pinnata* (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) is repeatedly and carefully fractionated, when the hydrocarbon is obtained in a more or less pure state. Its physical constants have been compared to those of some "*d*-cadinenes" and *l*-cadinene. There is a good agreement between the various *dextro*-rotatory hydrocarbons (vide Table II).

TABLE II

Hydrocarbon.	Source.	B.p.	Density	Refractive index.	Optical rotation
1. <i>l</i> -Cadinene.*	Regenerated from <i>l</i> -cadinene dihydro- chloride	134°-136°/11 mm.	d_{20}^{20} , 0.9819	n_D^{20} , 1.5079	[α] _D -125.2°
2. <i>d</i> -Cadinene**	West Indian Sandal- wood oil.	138°-140°/13	d_{18}^{18} , 0.9260	n_D^{18} , 1.5093	+380.7°
3. <i>d</i> -Cadinene†	African Copaiba balsam oil.	153°-154°/26	d_{18}^{18} , 0.9247	—	+50
4. <i>d</i> -Cadinene	<i>Hardwickia pinnata</i> Oleo-resin.	112°-114°/2	d_{20}^{20} , 0.9126	n_D^{20} , 1.5025	+38.3°

* Henderson and Robertson, *loc. cit.*

** Deussen *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1929, [1], 120, 121.

† Deussen, *Annalen*, 1912, 388, 143

Its molecular refraction (66.12) indicates that the hydrocarbon is a bicyclic sesquiterpene containing two double bonds (Semmler's classification of sesquiterpenes, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1037; Ruzicka, Meyer and Mingazzini, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 1345). This has been confirmed by the measurement of unsaturation by perbenzoic acid.

The hydrocarbon gives a good yield of a dihydrochloride, which has been found to be identical with *l*-cadinene dihydrochloride. However, it does not give some of the derivatives of *l*-cadinene, which involve the addition of addenda containing no hydrogen. Thus, whereas, *l*-cadinene gives good yields of a nitrosate and a nitrosochloride (Schreiner and Kremers, *Pharm. Arch.*, 1899, 2, 300) this hydrocarbon fails to give any of these derivatives. Attempts to characterise the sesquiterpene by a crystalline nitrosite or a solid tetrabromide were unsuccessful.

l-Cadinene is known to give a beautiful colour reaction with acetic and sulphuric acids (Wallach, *Annalen*, 1887, 288, 87; cf. Semmler and Jonas, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2076). This hydrocarbon does not give this reaction which appears to be characteristic of *l*-cadinene. A sample of pure *l*-cadinene has been prepared and some other colour reactions (vide experimental) of the two hydrocarbons have been examined and found to be somewhat different.

Like *l*-cadinene (Ruzicka and Stoll, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 92) it cannot be reduced by sodium and alcohol thus indicating the absence of conjugated double bonds. In conformity with this the hydrocarbon does not react with diazotised *p*-nitroaniline (Fieser's test for conjugation, Fieser and Campbell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 168).

Dehydrogenation.—The hydrocarbon has been dehydrogenated both by sulphur and selenium. On dehydrogenation by sulphur by Melville's method (*ibid.*, 1933, 55, 2462), cadalene (I) has been isolated. Traces of an azulene are also produced side by side. On selenium dehydrogenation, cadalene as well as azulene are obtained in somewhat better yields. The azulene has been identified to be *s*-guaiazulene (II). The production of azulene may be either due to the presence of some azulenic impurity (some sesquiterpene of the azulene group) or be due to some peculiarity of the molecule itself. The production of these two hydrocarbons from the crystalline ledol (III) is well established (Komppa and Nyman, *Compt. rend. trav. labor. Carlsberg*, 1938, 22, 272; *Chem. Abst.*, 1938, 32, 6234). Perhaps, in this case, the formation of azulene can be easily explained. But, the hydrochloride of the monocyclic sesquiterpene, *l*-*a*-curcumene (IV), also gives both these substances on selenium dehydrogenation (Carter, Copp. Rao, Simonsen and Subramaniam, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1504), a fact which cannot be easily explained. The conversion of cadalene into *s*-guaiazulene or *vice versa* due to prolonged heat-treatment is not likely and no such instance appears to have been recorded. Though physically azulenes appear to be less stable than the isomeric naphthalenes (Perrottet; Taub and Briner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 1260) they are compounds of considerable stability, as is evident from their usual method of formation (Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*; 1945, 258).

Ozonolysis.—A study of the products formed on ozonolysis of the hydrocarbon has clearly revealed that the sesquiterpene cannot be *d*-cadinene. The volatile degradation products consist entirely of formic acid and formaldehyde. These substances are absent from the products obtained on oxidation of *l*-cadinene with ozone (Ruzicka and Stoll, *loc. cit.* Semmler and Jonas, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2076). Amongst the non-volatile products, neutral compounds predominate, acidic substances are produced only to a very small extent. The neutral products have been separated by repeated fractionations in high vacuum. Analysis of the various fractions has indicated the presence of two compounds, $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ and $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$; the former is a diketone, whereas the latter contains an aldehydic group also.

Since the hydrocarbon yields *l*-cadinene dihydrochloride, the number of possible structures is limited. Ruzicka and Stoll (*loc. cit.*) assigned the structure (V) to *l*-cadinene, which has since then been modified due to the work of Campbell and Soffer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 417), who have shown it to be (VI). The *l*-cadinene dihydrochloride should then have structure (VII). Theoretically there can be nine hydrocarbons which can yield the dihydrochloride (VII). Since the hydrocarbon is not identical with *l*-cadinene (more appropriately called *l*-a-cadinene), only the remaining

eight structures need be taken into consideration. Because, this sesquiterpene gives formaldehyde and formic acid on ozonolysis, semicyclic double bond must be present in the molecule. A survey of these possible structures will reveal that only five such constitutions are possible, viz., (VIII), (IX), (X), (XI) and (XII). It is evident from these formulae that whereas only (VIII) can give rise to a diketone, $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$, all the remaining four substances can yield a $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ compound.

Location of the Nuclear Double Bond.—In order to distinguish between these structures the hydrocarbon has been further investigated. The procedure used is the same as that employed by Ruzicka and Sternbach for the location of the double bond of *dextro*-pimaric acid (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 124). The method has already been of much help in finally solving the structures of some of the sesquiterpenes of the cadalene group. Campbell and Soffer (*loc. cit.*) used it for modifying the structure of *l*-cadinene. The constitution of *iso*-zingiberene has been settled by Soffer, Steinhardt, Turner and Stebbins (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1520). Finally, use has been made of this procedure by Briggs and Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1338) in revising the older formula of copaene.

By the action of perbenzoic acid on the hydrocarbon, an unsaturated mono-oxide has been obtained. Usually the ethylenic linkage, which is on the carbon atom next to the fused carbon atoms, is attacked first (Soffer, Steinhardt, Turner and Stebbins, *loc. cit.*). On treatment with excess of magnesiummethyl iodide, the oxide ring is opened up introducing an additional methyl group in the molecule. The alcohol, thus obtained, is dehydrated with formic acid and the unsaturated hydrocarbon is dehydrogenated with selenium. In this way a mixture of naphthalenic hydrocarbons is obtained, which has been converted into molecular compounds with trinitrobenzene. On repeated crystallisation of the product from alcohol and finally from 80% acetic acid, a crystalline compound has been isolated, which has been identified to be that derived from 2-methylcadalene (XIII).

This product can only originate from the hydrocarbon (IX). Hence, the cadinenic fraction of the oil from the oleo-resin of *Hardwickia pinnata* has been shown to be a mixture of two isomeric hydrocarbons (VIII) and (IX). It is quite likely that the other "*d*-cadinenes" described in the literature may be similarly constituted.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Cadinenic Hydrocarbon

The cadinenic fraction of the essential oil from the oleo-resin of *Hardwickia pinnata* was carefully refractionated several times. The same fractionating column was used.

In this way, 70 g. of the hydrocarbon were obtained from 200 g. of the original fraction. The sesquiterpene was obtained as a colorless, quite mobile liquid, b.p. 112° - $114^{\circ}/4$ mm, d_{20}^{20} , 0.9126; n_D^{20} 1.5025; $[\alpha]_D$, $+38.3^{\circ}$ ($c = 4.89\%$ in benzene solution), $[R_L]_D = 66.12$; ($[R_L]_D$ for $C_{15}H_{24}$ $\bar{15}$ 66.14). (Found: C, 87.98; H, 11.89. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84 per cent).

The hydrocarbon (1.0 g.) was dissolved in dry ether (1 c.c.) and chilled to below -10° and saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. During saturation the hydrochloride had started separating out. The reaction mixture (practically colorless) was kept in an ice-saltbath at -15° for 12 hours. The solvent and excess of the gas were removed in a very minute current of dry air in vacuum. The residue was dissolved in hot alcohol (about 2-3 c.c.) containing a few drops of ether. The crystals were filtered off and recrystallised from ethyl acetate. The product was obtained in white needles, m.p. 117 - 18° , yield about 50%; $[\alpha]_D$, -36.0° ($c = 2.63\%$ in chloroform solution) (cf. Henderson and Robertson, *loc. cit.*).

Attempts to prepare a crystalline *nitrosate* or a *nitrosochloride* according to the method of Schreiner and Kremers (*loc. cit.*) were not successful.

Colour Reactions.—Pure *l*-cadinene was prepared from *l*-cadinene dihydrochloride by the action of anhydrous sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid by the method of Henderson and Robertson (*loc. cit.*). The sesquiterpene was obtained as a colorless, quite mobile liquid, b. p. 114° - $116^{\circ}/2$ mm.

Concentrated Sulphuric Acid:—To three drops of the terpene in glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.) three drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were added and the colour produced was noted immediately. The sequence of the colour changes for the two hydrocarbons was as follows.

l-Cadinene: colourless \rightarrow green \rightarrow blue \rightarrow fading of blue \rightarrow red pink (on warming in a water-bath for a few seconds).

d-Hydrocarbon: pink \rightarrow deep pink \rightarrow red \rightarrow deep red \rightarrow deep red (on warming as above).

Liebermann-Burchard Reaction:—(Usually used for sterols, etc., *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 1803; also *Chem. Zentr.*, 1890, I, 25). The hydrocarbon (one drop) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (2 c.c.). The solution was well shaken and carefully treated with a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid, just shaken and the colour changes observed:

l-Cadinene: yellow \rightarrow light green \rightarrow fades out to a very light brown.

d-Hydrocarbon: light green \rightarrow deep green \rightarrow blue green.

On warming the two solutions for a few minutes, both solutions became practically colorless.

Bromine in Acetic Acid:—Sabétay and Sabétay (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 199, 313) have recommended this colour reaction for the identification of azulene-yielding hydrocarbons.

To 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, bromine vapours were added till a deep orange solution was obtained. To this solution a drop of the terpene was added and the colour changes observed.

l-Cadinene: colorless \rightarrow colorless.

d-Hydrocarbon: colorless \rightarrow light blue \rightarrow deep blue (after 2 min.)

Vanillin-Sulphuric Acid (cf. Nisida and Uota, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1940, 48, 64).—One drop of the hydrocarbon was added to 3 c.c. of 95% alcohol containing 1% alcoholic vanillin (two drops). To the mixture concentrated sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) was very carefully added by the sides of the test tube. The colour changes at the junction of the two layers were observed.

$\frac{\text{Blue}}{\text{Red}} \rightarrow \frac{\text{Violet}}{\text{Red}} \rightarrow$ on shaking the mixture acquired a violet colour momentarily, which changed to deep red. Both the hydrocarbons exhibited practically the same colour changes.

Reduction with Sodium and Alcohol (cf. Ruzicka and Stoll, *loc. cit.*).—To a solution of the hydrocarbon (4 g.) in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.), sodium (10 g.), cut in small pieces, was introduced slowly (reflux condenser). After the addition, the mixture was refluxed till all the sodium had disappeared. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner with ether. After drying the extract, the solvent was removed and the residue distilled twice over sodium. The product distilled at 115°-116°/3 mm. and had practically the same physical constants, the molecular refraction 66.13 being in good agreement with that required for a bicyclic sesquiterpene containing two double bonds (66.14).

Dehydrogenation

Dehydrogenation with Sulphur.—Melville's procedure (*loc. cit.*) was followed and the product was worked up in the usual manner. Cadalene was isolated and identified as described under selenium dehydrogenation.

Dehydrogenation with Selenium (cf. Diels and Karstens, *Ber.*, 1927, 60, 2323).—The hydrocarbon (10 g.) and selenium (20 g.) were heated together in a 30 c.c. long-necked distillation flask (side tube plugged) carrying an air condenser in a potassium nitrate-sodium nitrite bath at 290°-300° for 15 hours. The heating was continued for another 15 hours at 300°-310°. The product was then directly distilled off in vacuum. The distillate was twice redistilled over sodium, when it was obtained as a deep blue, mobile oil (6.0 g.).

The product was taken up in light petroleum ether (30 c.c.), the blue solution was shaken with syrupy phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 7.0 c.c.) till the solvent layer had become practically colorless. Another similar extraction was carried out with phosphoric acid. The petroleum ether solution was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed; the residue was distilled over sodium and was obtained as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 150°-160°/15 mm, yield 2.5 g. The product was identified by conversion into its *picrate* as orange silky needles (alcohol), m.p. 114-15°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of cadalene *picrate* (m.p. 115-16°) remained undepressed.

The phosphoric acid solution containing the azulene was washed (twice) with light petrol and was covered with peroxide-free ether (30 c.c.) and diluted with ice-water under cooling, when the azulene was released and extracted out with ether. The solution was washed with water, dried and the ether removed, when a small amount of a strongly smelling, deep blue liquid was left. This was converted into its *picrate* as black crystals (alcohol), m. p. 120° and styphnate, m. p. 105-106°. Ruzicka and Haagen-

Smit (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, 14, 1108) have reported the m.p. of *s*-guaiazulene picrate as 121-22° and that of the styphnate as 105°-106° (Sherndal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 167; Pfau and Piattner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1936, 19, 858).

Ozonolysis

The terpene (15.0 g.) was dissolved in dry, alcohol-free ethyl acetate (125 c.c.). The solution was chilled in ice-salt-bath (Dewar's flask) and a rapid current of dry ozonised air was sucked in. The issuing gases were being led through water (30 c.c.). The ozonisation was continued till practically no ozone was absorbed by the solution as shown by the generation of iodine from a solution of potassium iodide-boric acid within a few minutes (about two minutes). After about 28 to 30 hours, the ozonisation was complete.

Formaldehyde was detected in the issuing gases, by the preparation of the characteristic dimedone derivative. To the aqueous solution, an alcoholic solution of dimethyldihydroresorcinol (0.5 g. in 3 c.c. of alcohol) and a drop of piperidine were added and the mixture left overnight. The crystals were filtered off and recrystallised from dilute methanol. The dimedone compound was obtained in colorless needles, m. p. 185-86°, mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 189°) was 188°.

Decomposition of the Ozonide.—The ozonised solution was transferred to a flask (250 c.c.) and the solvent was removed under vacuum at 30-40°, while a very thin current of dry air was being sucked in through it. The ozonide was obtained as a clear, practically colorless syrup. Water (75 c.c.) was added to the syrup, a reflux condenser attached and the mixture slowly heated on a water-bath the temperature of which was raised very slowly and taken to the boiling point during one hour. The top of the condenser was connected to a gas trap containing water (15 c.c.). The reaction mixture was finally heated on the water-bath for 3 hours more and left overnight (12 hours).

The water in the gas trap did not give the usual tests for the presence of acetone (Legal's test) or formaldehyde (Meyer, "Nachweis und Bestimmung Organischer Verbindungen", 1930 Ed., pp.60, 47).

Separation of the Products.—The reaction mixture containing the products of decomposition of the ozonide was shaken with ether (twice). The ether-soluble products were thus extracted. The combined ether extracts were washed once with water (10 c.c.) and the aqueous washing added to the main aqueous portion of the ether extraction (A). The ether extract was repeatedly extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution and thus separated into the acidic (B) and the neutral portions (C).

Product A.—The water-soluble portion was strongly acidic in character and reduced both the Tollen's reagent and Fehling's solution. Its reaction with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent was practically negative, only a very faint turbidity being obtained. It gave the characteristic reaction of *formic acid* with mercuric oxide (Mulliken and Huntress, "Identification of Pure Organic Compounds", Order 1, p. 179, 1946 Ed. Ruzicka and van Veen, *Annalen*, 1929, 468, 152).

Product B.—The sodium bicarbonate extract on acidification gave a small amount of a gum (ca. 1 g.) which was not examined further.

Product C.—The ether extract containing the neutral products was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the ether removed, when a thick reddish liquid (12.0 g.) was left. The liquid gave positive tests for the presence of carbonyl compounds (2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent, *m*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride reagent, etc.). It reduced Tollen's reagent and Fehling solution. The absence of enols was concluded by the insolubility of any portion in aqueous potash (10%) and the negative colour reactions with aqueous or alcoholic ferric chloride. There was no development of the colour with Schiff's reagent. The peroxides were also absent.

The product was carefully fractionated several times in high vacuum (1.92×10^{-3} mm.). Ultimately, two chief fractions were obtained.

Fraction I, b.p. $105^\circ\text{--}115^\circ/3.07 \times 10^{-2}$ mm. (2.0 g.) was redistilled, when a colorless, slightly viscous liquid, b.p. $134^\circ\text{--}140^\circ/4$ mm. was obtained. (Found: C, 75.04; H, 10.33. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 9.61 per cent). The substance gave negative results with Fuson's test (Fuson and Tullock, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1638), Tollen's reagent, Schiff's reaction, and Fehling's solution. It decolorised bromine in chloroform with evolution of hydrogen bromide. It reacted readily with 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent, but the product could not be recrystallised.

Fraction II, b. p. $105^\circ\text{--}110^\circ/1.92 \times 10^{-3}$ mm. was obtained as a viscous, pale yellow liquid in a yield of 2 g. (Found: C, 71.62; H, 10.00. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 70.6; H, 9.2 per cent). This fraction gave a positive test with Fuson's reagent and Tollen's reagent, but it did not respond to Schiff's reaction. Its semicarbazone was obtained as a white powder, m. p. $246\text{--}48^\circ$ with decomposition. The product was insoluble in benzene, alcohol, ethyl acetate, etc. and hence it could not be recrystallised.

Determining the Position of the Nuclear Double Bond

Preparation of the Mono-oxide.—To a chilled solution of the cadinenic sesquiterpene (21.3 g., 1 mol.) in chloroform (350 c.c.), a chilled chloroform solution (-5°) of perbenzoic acid (315 c.c., containing 15.4 g. of perbenzoic acid, 1 mol.) was added with stirring and cooling in a freezing mixture. After the addition the reaction mixture was left in the refrigerator for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, when a test portion did not liberate any iodine (starch solution indicator) from an acidified (acetic acid) solution of potassium iodide. The reaction mixture was transferred to a small separating funnel and extracted thrice with 300 c.c. portions of an aqueous solution of sodium thiosulphate and sodium carbonate (900 c.c. of water, 50 g. of sodium thiosulphate and 25 g. of sodium carbonate). It was finally washed once with water and allowed to dry (sodium sulphate).

The chloroform was distilled off and the residue was carefully fractionated thrice. The chief fraction, b. p. $122^\circ\text{--}126^\circ/2$ mm., was obtained as a colorless, mobile liquid, yield 11.0 g. It decolorised bromine in chloroform and did not react with 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, indicating the absence of any isomerisation of the oxide to the ketone.

Reaction with Grignard Reagent.—A Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (3.6 g., 0.15M), methyl iodide (28.4 g., 13.0 c.c., 0.20M) and anhydrous ether (150 c.c.).

The Grignard solution was chilled in a freezing mixture and the mono oxide (11.0 g., 0.05 M), dissolved in anhydrous ether (30 c.c.), was added slowly with swirling. The reaction mixture was kept in the ice-bath for 15 minutes more and was then allowed to reach the room temperature. The reaction mixture was finally refluxed for 45 hours, cooled and decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. This was extracted with ether several times and the red ether extract was successively washed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride, sodium bisulphite solution (to remove free iodine) and brine containing sodium carbonate. The practically colorless solution was dried (sodium sulphate), and the solvent removed, when 12.0 g. (100%) of a greenish, slightly viscous liquid were left. The crude Grignard reaction product (8.0 g.) was dehydrated by heating on a water-bath with 95% formic acid (25 c.c.) for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner and fractionated twice over sodium. The product was obtained as a colorless, somewhat viscous, pleasant smelling liquid, b. p. 120°-127°/4 mm., yield 4.5 g.

Isolation of 2-Methylcadalene.—The above dehydrated product (4.0 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating with selenium (8.0 g.) for 27 hours at 280°-310°. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with benzene (25 c.c.), and the extract was treated with norit, filtered and then refluxed over sodium for an hour. The decanted benzene solution was distilled to remove the solvent and the residue was carefully fractionated over sodium. The highest boiling fraction (II fraction), b.p. 142°-150°/8 mm. (1.0 g.) was treated with a solution of trinitrobenzene (1.0 g.) in hot alcohol (20 c.c.). The mixture was heated to boiling and allowed to crystallise, when yellow needles (0.90 g.), m.p. 105°-115°, were obtained. Two recrystallisations from alcohol and one from 80% acetic acid gave a small quantity of fine, silky, yellow needles, m. p. 167-68° (mixed m. p. with T. N. B. compound of 3-methylcadalene, m. p. 165°, was 140-145°) the m. p. of which could not be raised further (m. p. of T. N. B. compound of 2-methylcadalene, 168-69°).

2-Methylcadalene was regenerated from the T. N. B. compound and converted into its *picrate*, which crystallised from alcohol in red needles, m. p. 142-43° (m. p. of 2-methylcadalene picrate, 143-44°, Sukh Dev, *this Journal*, 1948, 25, 318).

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